

Neural Network-Based Estimation of Flexural Performance for Polymer Permeable Concrete

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Abstract:

Pervious concrete is increasingly used to reduce runoff water and improve water quality near pavements and parking lots, but highway pavement structures cannot use it due to its high porosity and reduced strength. To address the issue of lower flexural strength in permeable concrete, this study designs and conducts 11 different tests with varying mix ratios. The objective is to ensure that the resulting concrete satisfies both permeability and compression resistance requirements. The uniform test method is employed to measure the flexural strength of the concrete after a period of 28 days. This study employs neural networks to analyze the flexural

performance of polymer permeable concrete by considering various input factors such as cement consumption, water consumption, STA (4.75 to 9.5 mm stones), STB (9.5 to 16 mm stones), VAE (vinyl acetate-ethylene) polymer content, and SAP polymer content. The objective is to optimize the mix proportion of polymer permeable concrete and identify a suitable ratio that satisfies the requirements of pavement structural flexural performance.

Keywords: *Pervious concrete, bending resistance, compound polymer, BP neural network model.*

Introduction

After or during construction, inappropriate curing, vibration, shrinkage cracks, and workmanship reduce the structural performance of civil engineering infrastructure, as do material degradation and weathering, rebar corrosion, water seepage, loading conditions, environmental degradation, and crack formation by using new technologies, such as artificial intelligence (Nawaz, 2022), digital twin (Shoukat, 2023, 2022, 2021 & Niaz, 2021), big data, etc.

The eco-friendly permeability of concrete makes it an ideal material for sponge cities. Adding reinforcing materials like fly ash or fiber to

permeable concrete improves its flexural resistance, according to most current studies on its qualities (Lukman, 2020). Nevertheless, research on the flexural characteristics of polymer permeable concrete is limited. Changing the admixtures, ash ratio, and single gradation is the main method used to study its flexural qualities. The particle size of the aggregate, the bone-to-cement ratio, and other parameters can be controlled with a single aggregate (Li, 2022). Numerous factors influence the flexural performance of polymer permeable concrete. There is a long test cycle, a lot of material consumption, and a significant number of test groups required for system analysis.

Figure 1. BP Artificial Neural Network Analysis Process

Impervious surfaces, such as those formed by buildings and pavements, are expanding due to rapid urbanization. These surfaces produce stormwater runoff, which in turn causes flooding and reduces water quality (Mal, 2021). Getting reliable test findings fast is challenging. It is also possible for test data to be inaccurate

due to cross-season testing. To investigate how aggregate gradation, water consumption, mud consumption, single-mixed polymer, and double-mixed polymer affect the flexural performance of permeable concrete, this study utilizes the BP neural network analysis method and designs the test using the uniform test

method (Shirmard, 2022). The mining business is highly competitive and increasingly dependent on product performance and energy efficiency (Tang, 2022). Microchannels can be utilized for the purpose of improving the dispersion of heat, leading to enhanced performance and reliability of semiconductors. Microchannels have the potential to be employed in order to enhance the dispersion of heat, hence resulting in improved performance and reliability of semiconductors (Cheng, 2022). A theoretical basis is provided by an analysis of concrete's flexural characteristics. Figure 1 depicts the process flow of the BP neural network analysis approach.

Materials and Methods

Test process

Raw materials P·O42. grade 5 port-land cement. Coarse aggregate ST A particle size 4.75 ~ 9.5 mm stone; ST B particle size 9.5 ~ 16 mm stones. VAE latex powder (ethylene vinyl acetate polymer), model number FY-31. Powdered SAP [polyacrylate (sodium salt) super absorbent resin]. Tap water.

Experimental mix ratio design: based on the research experience in the distribution intervals of aggregate density, bone-glue ratio, water-cement ratio, polymer content percentage, etc., the range of materials used for each cubic meter of permeable concrete is analyzed and given, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Material Range of Each Cubic Meter of Permeable Concrete

Cement (kg/m ³)	Water (L)	ST A(4.75 ~ 9.5 mm) (kg/m ³)	ST B(9.5 ~ 16 mm) (kg/m ³)	VAE(kg/m ³)	SAP(kg/m ³)
203 ~ 318	51 ~ 127	0 ~ 1275	1250 ~ 0	0 ~ 47.7	0 ~ 3.18

Experimental preparation. Use the pure-slurry-wrapping stone method to stir manually. Stir the dried gravel evenly with all the cement, SAP, and VAE; add 2/3 of water and stir for 1 minute. After all the aggregate surfaces are wet, add the

remaining calculated amount of water, stir again, and then discharge and hammer into shape. The situation after on-site mixing, mold installation, and mold removal is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. After On-Site Mixing, Formwork Installation and Dismantling

Experimental test methods: A permeable concrete specimen of 40 mm × 40 mm × 160

mm was used and placed into the DKZ-5000 cement electric flexural machine to measure its

28-day flexural strength. The cross-section condition of the specimen after failure is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Cross Section of Specimen after Failure

Training of neural network model

Using the five influencing factors of aggregate gradation, water consumption, cement, VAE, and SAP as input variables and the 28-day flexural strength index as the output variable, a 5-8-8-1 BP neural network model was established for experimental analysis. According to Table 1, the number of materials for one test was determined, and 11 groups of tests were designed using the uniform test method. The results are shown in Table 2. The total amount of aggregates for gravel STA and STB is 20.63kg. 90% of the training samples are randomly selected from Table 2, 5% are used for validity verification, and 5% are used for actual testing for direct training. The model training results are shown in Figure 4.

Table 2. Tests of different mix ratios and measured flexural strength

serial number	Cement (kg)	Water (mL)	ST A(4.75 ~ 9.5 mm) (kg/m ³)	ST B(9.5 ~ 16 mm) (kg/m ³)	VAE(g)	SAP(g)	28 d Flexural strength f_t (Mpa)
B1	3.284	1400	4.13	16.50	309	31	1.35
B2	3.470	1500	10.32	10.31	695	10	2.37
B3	3.656	1720	16.51	4.12	232	46	2.2
B4	3.842	1780	0.00	20.63	618	26	1.75
B5	4.028	1932	6.19	14.44	155	5	1.4
B6	4.214	1922	12.38	8.25	541	41	3.23
B7	4.400	1720	18.57	2.06	77	21	2.95
B8	4.586	1720	2.07	18.56	463	0	2.18
B9	4.772	1888	8.26	12.38	0	36	2.6
B10	4.958	1888	14.44	6.19	386	15	2.25
B11	5.144	2205	20.63	0.00	772	51	2.5

Figure 5 is the change curve of the mean square error with the number of times in the BP neural network training process. It can be seen that the mean square error of the curve gradually decreases as the number of training times

increases. When the number of training times reaches 25 times, the target mean square error square. The sum is 1.6634×10^{-12} , the network converges to the specified error.

Figure 4. The Variation of Mean Square Error of BP Neural Network Training with Frequency

Results

The method of proportional change of test factors (Zhang, 2022 & Rehman, 2023) is used to adjust the test factors to obtain each single factor test, and then use the neural network model to simulate, and the simulation results are reliable.

Aggregate gradation

Aggregate is the structural skeleton embedded within permeable concrete. Its particle size and gradation will directly affect the strength of permeable concrete. The BP neural network simulation test was used to analyze the influence of STA and STB on the flexural strength of specimens under different gradations, as shown in Figure 5.

The observation can be made from Figure 6 that there is a gradual increase in the flexural strength of permeable concrete at the 28-day mark when the quantity of aggregate STA is increased.

Water consumption

Water cement ratio cannot be packaged in order to assess test results because, unlike conventional concrete, permeable concrete only follows a linear relationship between water cement ratio and strength within a small range. This means that the ratio of water cement cannot be bundled. The link between cement dosage and flexural strength is depicted in Figures 6 and 7, which illustrates the relationship under

different given water consumption conditions when STA: STB = 3:1 and 4:0.

Figure 5. Effect of Different Aggregate Grades on Bending Strength

Figure 6. Bending Strength at STA:STB = 3:1 Water and Cement Usage Levels

It can be seen from Figures 6 and 7 that when the water consumption is ≤ 1600 ml, the flexural performance of permeable concrete is better. When the water consumption exceeds 1800 ml, its flexural performance is poor. To obtain good flexural properties, water consumption must be strictly controlled.

When the water consumption W is 1600 mL, adding 4% to 9% VAE polymer can reduce part of the cement consumption and improve the

flexural performance of permeable concrete. 8. 3% ~ 25%.

Figure 7. Bending Strength at STA:STB = 4:0 Water and Cement Usage Levels

Discussion

Researchers conducted eleven sets of tests using the uniform test method to analyze the impact of five influencing factors on the 28-day flexural strength of permeable concrete. These factors include water consumption, cement dosage, gradation of STA and STB, VAE dosage, and SAP dosage. The five influencing factors affect the flexural strength of polymer-permeable concrete, ranked from strong to weak: the flexural strength of polymer-permeable concrete is affected by the five influencing factors in the following order of strength: water consumption > STA > cement F7. To the east of F7, between the south of the mine and the main railway line, 2 karst-concentrated development areas have been delineated. Numbered Y4 and Y5, with an overall length of 1500 m and a width of 400 m. It is large in scale and has a total of 158 karst development points interpreted in the area. The low resistance of the high-density electric method is more prominent, and the low resistance of the transient electromagnetic method is particularly complicated. Karst collapse is seen locally on the surface. Multiple layers of karst are found in multiple boreholes, up to 5 layers, and single-layer karst caves are up

to 6.7 m, which is the potential karst ground collapse risk area.

Based on the analysis of the vertical distribution characteristics of karst, the apparent resistivity section shows that the low-resistivity body in the shallow part is relatively stable and is inferred to be the Quaternary system. The local distortion in the shallow part is analyzed as collapse and potential collapse. The section elevation is as low as 60 m to -20 m. The frequency of resistive bodies increases significantly, and it is inferred that this layer is a layer with relatively developed karst. The apparent resistivity gradually increases from -20 m to depth, and the karst development weakens. Based on the analysis of karst development data in the entire region, the maximum elevation of karst development is 69.345 m and the minimum elevation is -43.436 m, average development elevation 36.49 m, and the elevations of 20 to 60 m account for more than 65% of the entire area, indicating that the elevation of 20 to 60 m is the main depth for karst development in the entire area (Ganapathi, 2020 & Sebaaly, 2018).

The filling conditions of dissolution holes in the working area can be roughly divided into three types: fully filled, semi-filled, and hollow. The dissolved pores are mostly filled with clay and are densely cemented; some are unfilled and have a honeycomb shape. A total of 22 caves were exposed through 23 boreholes during this construction, including 1 fully-filled cave, accounting for 4.5%, the filling material is silty clay; there are 12 semi-filled caves, accounting for 54.5%, the filling is silty clay or fine sand; there are 9 cavities, accounting for 40.9%.

Conclusion

After a comprehensive analysis of the hydrogeological conditions and karst development characteristics of a cement limestone mine, the conclusion is as follows: this cement limestone mine is a karst fissure type direct water-filled mine, and the hydrogeological conditions are medium type. The mine rock formation is weakly water-rich, with shallow karst development and close contact with

surface water. The area below the lower limit of karst development (-100 m) is approximately a water-proof layer. The karst development areas are clearly divided and zoned, and are closely related to the lithology and syncline axis.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Cheng, Y., Zhou, K., Wang, J., Cui, S., Yan, J., De Maeyer, P., & Van de Voorde, T. (2022). Regional metal pollution risk assessment based on a long short-term memory model: A case study of the South Altai Mountain mining area, China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 379, 134755. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134755>
- Ganapathi, H., & Phukan, M. (2020). Environmental Hazards of limestone mining and adaptive practices for environment management plan. *Environmental Processes and Management: Tools and Practices*, 121-134. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-38152-3_8
- Li, Q., Sui, W., Sun, B., Li, D., & Yu, S. (2022). Application of TOPSIS water abundance comprehensive evaluation method for karst aquifers in a lead zinc mine, China. *Earth Science Informatics*, 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12145-021-00730-2>
- Lukman, L. (2020). Feasibility Analysis of Limestone Industry. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(09). <https://repository.uinjkt.ac.id/dspace/handle/123456789/57723>
- Mal, U., & Adhikari, K. (2021). Groundwater quality and hydrological stress induced by Lower Gondwana open cast coal mine. *Journal of Earth System Science*, 130, 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12040-020-01486-x>
- Nawaz, S. A., Li, J., Bhatti, U. A., Shoukat, M. U., & Ahmad, R. M. (2022). AI-based object detection latest trends in remote sensing, multimedia and agriculture applications. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 13, 1041514. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2022.1041514>
- Niaz, A., Shoukat, M. U., Jia, Y., Khan, S., Niaz, F., & Raza, M. U. (2021, October). Autonomous driving test method based on digital twin: A survey. In *2021 International Conference on Computing, Electronic and Electrical Engineering (ICE Cube)* (pp. 1-7). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICECube53880.2021.9628341>
- Ozturk, H. I., & Kutay, M. E. (2014). An artificial neural network model for virtual Superpave asphalt mixture design. *International Journal of Pavement Engineering*, 15(2), 151-162. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10298436.2013.808341>
- Rehman, S., Algarni, S., Imtiaz, M., Alqahtani, T., ElSeabee, F. A. A., Jamshed, W., ... & El Din, S. M. (2023). Inclined magnetic force impact on cross nanoliquid flowing with widening shallow and heat generating by using artificial neural network (ANN). *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*, 103690. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2023.103690>
- Sebaaly, H., Varma, S., & Maina, J. W. (2018). Optimizing asphalt mix design process using artificial neural network and genetic algorithm. *Construction and Building Materials*, 168, 660-670. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2018.02.118>
- Shirmard, H., Farahbakhsh, E., Heidari, E., Beiranvand Pour, A., Pradhan, B., Müller, D., & Chandra, R. (2022). A comparative study of convolutional neural networks and conventional machine learning models for lithological mapping using remote sensing data. *Remote Sensing*, 14(4), 819. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14040819>
- Shoukat, M. U., Yan, L., Zhang, J., Cheng, Y., Raza, M. U., & Niaz, A. (2023). Smart home for enhanced healthcare: exploring human machine

interface oriented digital twin model. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-023-16875-9>

Shoukat, M. U., Yan, L., Zou, B., Zhang, J., Niaz, A., & Raza, M. U. (2022, November). Application of Digital Twin Technology in the Field of Autonomous Driving Test. In *2022 Third International Conference on Latest trends in Electrical Engineering and Computing Technologies (INTELLECT)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/INTELLECT55495.2022.9969184>

Shoukat, M. U., Yu, S., Shi, S., Li, Y., & Yu, J. (2021, October). Evaluate the connected autonomous vehicles infrastructure using digital twin model based on cyber-physical combination of intelligent network. In *2021 5th*

CAA International Conference on Vehicular Control and Intelligence (CVCI) (pp. 1-6). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVCI54083.2021.9661190>

Tang, K., Da Wang, Y., Mostaghimi, P., Knackstedt, M., Hargrave, C., & Armstrong, R. T. (2022). Deep convolutional neural network for 3D mineral identification and liberation analysis. *Minerals Engineering*, 183, 107592. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mineng.2022.107592>

Zhang, M., Zhang, K., Ai, X., Liang, X., Zhang, Q., Chen, H., & Zou, X. (2022). Theory-guided electrocatalyst engineering: From mechanism analysis to structural design. *Chinese Journal of Catalysis*, 43(12), 2987-3018. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1872-2067\(22\)64103-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1872-2067(22)64103-2)